

PREreview Slack Community Guidelines

We require everyone participating in the PREreview Slack community to follow these community participation guidelines.

Expected behavior

By participating in our Slack community, you agree to adhere to these guidelines:

1. Treat others with respect and inclusivity at all times
2. Foster a collaborative environment
3. Post relevant and appropriate content for each channel—do not post spam, advertisements, or irrelevant self-promotion
4. Respect the privacy and confidentiality of everyone here
5. Maintain kindness, professionalism, and integrity in all of your interactions here

How to use the channels

Welcome to PREreview Community Slack! Please feel free to introduce yourselves in the [#introductions](#) channel if you have not already done so.

- 🙋 [#help](#): Let us know if you run into any difficulty using PREreview. We'll help you figure it out as soon as possible.
- 📅 [#events](#): Searching for an Open Reviewers training or a PREreview conference appearance? Have your own event to share? This is the channel for you.
- 🗣️ [#live-reviews](#): Here you can find the details of upcoming collaborative preprint review events.
- 📢 [#community-news](#): Keep up with all the latest developments from PREreview and share relevant news you think other community members will appreciate!

- 🚀 **#jobs-and-opportunities**: This is the channel to check out if you are looking for your new career step, or you want to share job & training openings of your own.
- 🌐 **#translation-general**: Want to help us make PREreview more inclusive, here is the general channel to discuss our translation work.
- 🔍 **#request-a-review**: Have a preprint you would like to get reviewed? Share it here to let the PREreview community know. Remember to include your link or DOI and a summary of the paper. Also check out this channel for review requests coming in authors posting on bioRxiv, SciELO Preprints, and Preprints.org powered by COAR Notify.
- 🌟 **#share-a-review**: Point people towards PREreviews you've authored and invite them to contribute their own. Remember to add your link. Also check out automated notifications of new reviews published on [PREreview.org](https://prereview.org).

Please note that you can also **connect your public PREreview profile to Slack** to help community members find you across platforms. To do so, sign into [PREreview.org](https://prereview.org), click on “Menu,” then click on “My details” under “My account.” You’ll find a toggle there that lets you turn the connection between your public profile and Slack account on and off.

Reporting violations

Please report any behavior that you think violates these guidelines by emailing report@prereview.org or by filling out [this anonymous form](#). You can learn more about how we handle reports like this by reviewing the full [PREreview Code of Conduct](#).

How to use Slack

If you would like more tips on how to make the most out of your experience in our Slack community workspace, then please refer to this [Slack Quick Start Guide](#) developed by the wonderful people at The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE). (Woodley, Louise, & Pratt, Catherine. (2020). Slack quick start guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3763730>)

Short link to this document: <https://bit.ly/Slack-guidelines>

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